

D6.2

Release of AGROSUS Website

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PROJECT ACRONYM: AGROSUS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The project website is one of the primary communication channels where all project public information will be updated. It was created following the project identity and is focused on the main project objectives and aspects such as the Biogeographical regions and the stakeholder activities planned to be produced during the project lifetime.

It is a live channel with static and dynamic information that will be updated thanks to the contribution of the project partners.

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FEUGA	Tamara Rodríguez Silva
Beneficiaries	Deliverable Co-Author (S)
All partners	
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Type of deliverable	R	Document, report	
	DMP	Data Management Plan	
	DEC	Websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	X
	ETHICS		

Dissemination level	PU	Public, fully open, e.g., web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page))	X
	SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

Revision history

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Contents

1. WEB STRUCTURE	5
1.1. Header, Body, Footer	5
1.2. Primary Menu and submenus	6
2. PROJECT	7
3. BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGIONS	10
3.1. Regional pages.....	11
4. MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH	12
5. NEWS	14
5.1. Events	14
6. KNOWLEDGE CENTER	15
7. CONTACT	17

Figure Index

Figure 1 Header	5
Figure 2 Header Body	5
Figure 3 HeaderFooter	5
Figure 4 Submenus example	6
Figure 5 Project landing page	7
Figure 6 Objectives page	8
Figure 7 Work packages page.....	9
Figure 8 Linked projects page.....	10
Figure 9 Biogeographical regions page.....	11
Figure 10 Example of regional page: Pannonian case	12
Figure 11 Multi-Actor Approach page.....	13
Figure 12 News page	14
Figure 13 Events page.....	15
Figure 14 Knowledge center page	16
Figure 15 Contact page.....	17

1. WEB STRUCTURE

1.1. Header, Body, Footer

Following the project identity, the AGROSUS website was created following homogeneous corporate elements such as the header, the body and the footer and the right box links to social networks.

Figure 1 Header

Figure 2 Header Body

Figure 3 HeaderFooter

1.2. Primary Menu and submenus

Six main menus will be shown with scroll-down submenus linked to different pages as follows:

- Project
 - About
 - Objectives
 - Work packages
 - Linked projects
- News
 - Events
- Biogeographical regions
 - Arctic Region
 - Continental Region
 - Black Sea Region
 - Mediterranean Region
 - Alpine Region
 - Atlantic Region
 - Boreal Region
 - Macaronesian Region
 - Pannonian Region
 - Steppic Region
 - Anatolian Region
- Multi-Actor Approach
- Knowledge center
- Contact

Figure 4 Submenus example

2. PROJECT

The homepage includes all key messages and quick links to different sections inside the website. It comprises different content banners related to objectives, Biogeographical regions, Latest news, Knowledge Center, and Partners logo carrousel.

Figure 5 Project landing page

It is also the parent page of some submenus pages as:

- **About:** Contains a short paragraph about how we got started, project partners detailed information, including team members in an accordion format that shows each partner's information when clicking on the Institution Name, and Expert Advisory Board description and members.

- **Objectives:** Descriptive section including from general to specific project objectives.

Figure 6 Objectives page

- **Work packages:** This section shows the project flow structured in 7 interrelated Work Packages, briefly described later.

Figure 7 Work packages page

- **Linked projects:** Page includes some linked projects with their logo, short description and link to their webpage.

Figure 8 Linked projects page

3. BIOGEOGRAPHICAL REGIONS

The main Biogeographical regions page shows a map where project partners will carry out the different methods within and between the **11 biogeographic regions in conventional, organic, and mixed farming systems**. Also, a link to each of the regions is included.

Figure 9 Biogeographical regions page

3.1. Regional pages

Each Biogeographical region has its own page where the main information is provided. It is composed of static information (fixed by the beginning of the project) related to the main region description and mini cards describing the different experiments carried out in the different countries involved, including pedoclimatic conditions (i.e., Soil Type, Average Temperature and Precipitations) and key figures (farming systems, crops, crops-linked groups, and a number of co-creation and co-validation workshops expected).

This section will be completed with dynamic information to show nurturing from news and related events and an image gallery or other materials developed during the project's lifetime.

Figure 10 Example of regional page: Pannonian case

4. MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH

AGROSUS is a multi-actor approach project, and the project strategy is shown in this section. Lead by an illustration where the different stakeholders engage at the different stages in the Regional Stakeholders Communities, representing cultural, physical and mechanical, biological and biotechnological, as well as preventive Strategies.

The section continues describing the project objectives, and it is followed by another illustration where the different interaction activities with stakeholders are located on a map.

To end with, four KPI's related to the AGROSUS Multi-Actor Approach strategy are described:

- 14 Regional Stakeholders Community (RSC)
- 24 Crop-linked groups (CLG)
- 19 Co-creation workshops
- 38 Co-validation workshops

MULTI-ACTOR APPROACH

INDEPENDENT STAKEHOLDERS INVOLVED

- Farmers
- Advisors
- Researchers
- Policy makers
- Associations, NGOs
- EUF variety

TWO DEVELOPMENT STAGES

Co-creation

Co-validation

14 Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSC)

11 Regional Meetings

30 Co-creation Workshops

68 Co-validation Workshops

SHORT, MEDIUM & LONG-TERM SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT

The multi-actor approach

The consortium integrates a multi actor approach for farmers' decision making and for including the different perspectives from stakeholders to decision-makers that regulate and administer policies.

In summary, AGROSUS will rely on:

1. expanded knowledge on problematic weeds on European agriculture, current weeding techniques, and problems encountered by farmers and advisors (around 500 farmers and advisors will be contacted for surveys, workshops and discussion groups)
2. advanced detection tools
3. establishment of cultural, mechanical, physical, biological, and bioecological AS in 68 short-term experimental units sprayed all over Europe
4. actions carried out with stakeholders and policy makers to promote the most appropriate initiatives at the field, administration and regulatory levels, and
5. technology transfer and training of stakeholders for prevention and management of weeds.

The tools and strategies designed will be developed, in collaboration with stakeholders, for the most problematic weeds of the different regions.

INFORM
COMMUNICATION & COORDINATION 24 Stakeholders

ASSESS
SURVEYS Farmers

INVOLVE
IN PERSON INTERVIEWS All stakeholders
CO-CREATION WORKSHOPS All stakeholders
CO-VALIDATION WORKSHOPS All stakeholders

COLLABORATE
JOINT REGIONAL EXTERNAL EVENTS Initiatives and other related projects

14 Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSC)
14 regional administrative units, 1 in each RSC including field visits and discussion groups

24 Crop-Linked Groups (CLG)
Around each experimental unit in the regional level covering the 11 biogeographic regions for co-creation and co-validation of actions undertaken in the other 9 RSC during the project

19 Co-creation workshops
The co-creation stage will consist of a series of generative meetings, in-person interviews, and co-creation workshops with the stakeholders included in the CLGs of each RSC, for co-decision about the best AS to be implemented in WP3

38 Co-validation workshops
The co-validation stage will consist of a series of co-validation workshops (one per crop) where the stakeholders included in the CLGs of each RSC, for feedback and improvement of AGROSUS AS

Figure 11 Multi-Actor Approach page

5. NEWS

A blog page will be updated with posts related to the project, both the ones delivered by the project and others related somehow. New ones or featured ones will also appear in the home section.

They will all be categorized and tagged to increase online positioning but also to allow anchoring this specific news to the corresponding Biogeographical Regional pages.

Figure 12 News page

5.1. Events

An event page will be updated with events related to the project. As described in the news section, new or featured ones will also appear at the home section.

Figure 13 Events page

6. KNOWLEDGE CENTER

Under this section, all public materials will be published and linked to different social networks and repositories.

It includes:

- **Link to AGROSUS ZENODO repository**
- **Communication materials:** Logos, Book of Style, Roll-Up, Banners, Posters...
- **Dissemination materials:** Leaflets, posters...
- **Scientific articles:** pre-prints, open access papers, etc.
- **Deliverables:** only when they are considered as public.

Figure 14 Knowledge center page

7. CONTACT

A contact form hangs from this section and will be received by info@agrosus.eu

The screenshot shows the 'Contact Us' page of the AGROSUS website. The page features a green header with the AGROSUS logo and navigation links: Project, News, Biogeographical regions, Multi-Actor Approach, Knowledge center, and Contact. Below the header is a large banner image of a sunflower field with the text 'Contact Us' overlaid. The main content area is titled 'Get In Touch' and contains a contact form with the following fields: First Name, Last Name, Email Address, I am Interested in, and a large text area for the Message. A green 'Send Message' button is located at the bottom right of the form. On the right side of the page, there is a vertical stack of social media icons for Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, and YouTube, along with a plus sign icon.

Figure 15 Contact page